

S1 Table. Discriminant function analysis with Principal Component scores for classification of nine call types.

		Call type									Total
		<i>Ar-1</i>	<i>Chuff</i>	<i>eee</i>	<i>Er</i>	<i>Growl</i>	<i>Haer</i>	<i>Hiss</i>	<i>Roar</i>	<i>Ar-2</i>	
Number of Correct Classification	<i>Ar-1</i>	1631	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	89	1725
	<i>Chuff</i>	0	428	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	428
	<i>eee</i>	0	2	66	0	37	0	0	0	0	105
	<i>Er</i>	0	0	0	214	0	48	0	296	70	628
	<i>Growl</i>	0	12	15	0	40	0	0	0	0	67
	<i>Haer</i>	2	0	0	68	0	29	0	21	6	126
	<i>Hiss</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	208	0	3	211
	<i>Roar</i>	0	0	0	7	0	11	0	69	4	91
	<i>Ar-2</i>	58	0	0	222	0	109	2	414	1149	1954
Rate of Correct Classification	<i>Ar-1</i>	94.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	5.2	100
	<i>Chuff</i>	0	100.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
	<i>eee</i>	0	1.9	62.9	0	35.2	0	0	0	0	100
	<i>Er</i>	0	0	0	34.1	0	7.6	0	47.1	11.1	100
	<i>Growl</i>	0	17.9	22.4	0	59.7	0	0	0	0	100
	<i>Haer</i>	1.6	0	0	54.0	0	23.0	0	16.7	4.8	100
	<i>Hiss</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.6	0	1.4	100
	<i>Roar</i>	0	0	0	7.7	0	12.1	0	75.8	4.4	100
	<i>Ar-2</i>	3.0	0	0	11.4	0	5.6	0.1	21.2	58.8	100